

REPORT:

A3.2.4: Test protocol for surface roughness

Work package 3

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This report was written as part of activity 3.2.4 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written by:

Loïc Crouzier
Christina Pecnik

LNE
IMTAG

Loic.Crouzier@lne.fr
cpecnik@imtag.ch

EMPIR

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1. Scope

This report addresses the activity A3.2.4 defined in the JRP protocol as:

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A3.2.4 M11	<p>LNE with support from IMTAG, IPQ and CEA will investigate the existing metrology for roughness from microscale to macroscale. LNE, IMTAG, IPQ and CEA will by October 2022 (M17) develop a test protocol for surface roughness ensuring traceability to national standard and conformity to existing normative standards. The test protocol will enable to measure the key material properties related to interfaces and key performance parameters of microfluidic connections identified in A3.1.1 and A3.1.5.</p> <p>The test protocol will be used for building the transfer standards in A2.4.2. The protocol will be used also for testing the transfer standards once they are built, and this testing will in turn lead to updating the protocol by February 2024 (M33).</p>	LNE , IMTAG, IPQ, CEA

2. Definitions

Surface roughness

A roughness value of a surface can either be calculated on a profile (line) or on a surface (area).

The area roughness parameter S_a is defined as the arithmetic mean height parameter of the absolute of the ordinate values of the scale-limited surface [1]. It expresses, as an absolute value, the difference in height of each point compared to the arithmetical mean of the surface. S_a is calculated using the following formula:

$$S_a = \frac{1}{A} \iint |z(x, y)| dx dy$$

with A as the value of the evaluation area [μm^2] or [mm^2], $z(x, y)$ as the height ordinate value resp. the normal distance from the reference surface to the scale-limited surface, (x, y) represents a position with the coordinate values x and y .

Figure 1: Schematic representation of S_a [2].

The profile roughness parameter R_a is defined as the arithmetic mean height parameter of the absolute of the ordinate values resp. of a line [3]. R_a is calculated using the following formula:

$$R_a = \frac{1}{l_e} \int_0^{l_e} |z(x)| dx$$

with l_e as the evaluation length resp. the length in the direction of the x-axis used for identifying.

Figure 2 : Schematic representation of R_a [4].

3. Classification of methods for measuring surface roughness

ISO 25178-6:2010 [5] describes a classification system for methods used primarily for the measurement of surface texture. These methods can be divided into three categories:

- **Line-profiling method**, which are methods that produces a two-dimensional graph or profile of the surface irregularities as measurement date, which may be represented mathematically as a height function $z(x)$. This category includes instruments that were developed specifically to measure line profiles like contact stylus scanning, phase-shifting interferometer or optical differential profiler.
- **Areal-topography method**, which are methods that produces a topographical image of a surface, which may be represented mathematically as a height function $z(x,y)$ of two independent variables (x,y) . This category includes instruments that were developed specifically for areal-topography measurement like **confocal microscopy**, coherence-scanning interferometry, scanning electron microscopy stereoscopy or **atomic force microscopy**.
- **Areal-integrating method**, which are methods that produces a representative area of a surface and produces numerical results that depends on area-integrated properties of the surface texture. This category includes instruments that were developed specifically for area-integrating measurement like integrated light scatter or angle-resolved light scatter.

Confocal microscopy

The confocal microscopy method is described in section 3.3.6 of the standard ISO 25178-6:2010 [5]. Confocal microscopy is a method of measuring surface topography whereby the image of a hole illuminated by the light source is projected through a lens onto the surface under investigation. The light is then reflected through the lens to a second hole placed in front of a detector and acting as a spatial filter.

ISO 25178-602:2010 [6] specifies the design and metrological characteristics of an instrument used to measure surface texture using a confocal sensor.

Atomic Force microscopy

The atomic force microscope (AFM) is a type of local probe microscope used to visualise the topography of the surface of a sample. The atomic force microscope therefore allows the surface of a sample to be scanned by means of a very fine tip positioned at the free end of a flexible micro-lever, which can move in all directions in space, thanks to a piezoelectric tube (usually). The analysis of the bending of the micro-lever allows the exact path of the tip to be determined, as well as the measurement of the interaction forces between it and the sample.

4. Metrological limitations

Annex A of ISO 25178-6:2010 [5] defines the metrological limits associated with the measurement of surface texture. The key parameters to consider when choosing a suitable method for surface roughness measurement are the range and resolution of the instruments.

Thus, the lateral resolution is limited by the spatial resolution of the sensor, such as the diffraction limit of an optical microscope or the radius of curvature of the tip of a contact instrument.

Vertical resolution is usually limited by the noise or resolution of the measuring instrument.

The lateral range is limited by the size of the measured area.

The vertical range is limited by the maximum travel distance in the Z direction.

It is therefore important to select the appropriate method according to the specifications of the surface to be measured. Table 1 gives the metrological limits associated with the measurement of surface texture by AFM and confocal microscopy.

Table 1 : metrological limits associated with the measurement of surface texture by AFM and confocal microscopy.

Method	Lateral resolution	Vertical resolution	Lateral range	Vertical range
Atomic Force Microscopy	Tip radius < 10nm	< 1 nm	Several tens of μm^*	5 – 10 μm
Confocal Microscopy	$\sim 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ [7-9]	$\sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ [7-9]	Field of view: Few 10 μm up to few 1000 μm XY stage: up to 10mm - 100mm	<1mm up to several mm

* curvature effects may occur for large displacements on some instruments

5. Traceability

Traceability of Atomic Force Microscope measurements

At the nanometre scale, the chain of traceability is represented by the pyramid shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 : Measurement traceability pyramid relative to dimensional measurements with the AFM [10].

The definition of the metre, as defined in the SI, is at the top and the measurements, made for example with an AFM, form the base. Between these two blocks, an unbroken chain of comparisons and calibrations is established to provide consistency and comparability of results.

On the lower part of the pyramid, the traceability of the measurements carried out in microscopy (AFM) is ensured by the calibration of the instruments through a calibration system. On the lower part of the pyramid, the traceability of the measurements carried out in microscopy (AFM) is ensured by the calibration of the instruments thanks to a transfer standard generally materialised by a network of 1D or 2D patterns whose dimensional properties (XY period and Z step height) are known and reported in a calibration certificate. In order not to break this chain of traceability, the grating used as a transfer standard must be calibrated using a reference instrument that will be able to establish a link between the practical realisation of the definition of the metre in the SI and the measurement made by the operator. For this purpose, one of the most common instruments found in National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) is the metrological AFM (mAFM)

This reference instrument, dedicated to the calibration of transfer standards, uses laser interferometers as position sensors in order to determine in a traceable way, for each pixel of the image, the relative position of the tip with respect to the sample. To date, there are only about thirty equivalent instruments in the world.

6. Test protocols

Roughness measurement using Atomic Force Microscope

To perform roughness measurements using Atomic Force Microscope it is recommended that the following instructions be followed:

- For open-loop systems (without a servo system), scanning had to be initiated before measurement. For open loop systems (with a servo system), the scan should be started before the measurement. A few hours of thermalization is recommended to avoid drift of the piezoelectric ceramics.
- If the system has a protective housing, it should be closed.
- It is recommended to wait at least one hour before starting measurements to allow the system to stabilise thermally (instrument, tip, sample).
- It is requested to work around the neutral point on the scanner (zero supply voltage)
- The X-axis of the grid should be aligned with the axis of the lever.
- The fast scan axis must be parallel to the lever axis.
- Depending on the Z-axis, the resolution should be adjusted as best as possible by the user.
- The servo control of the tip should be optimised by the user.
- The installation of the roughness measurement system must be free of vibrations.
- The AFM tip should have a sufficiently small radius of curvature to follow the surface topography.
- The scan size and image resolution (number of pixels per scan line) should be adjusted.

To determine the surface roughness and its homogeneity, make a minimum of 5 measurements, changing the area between each measurement.

To calculate the roughness S_a , it is necessary to use image processing software. The processing steps to be carried out are generally the following:

- Extraction of the topographic image (calibrated).
- Straightening of the topographic image.
- Sequencing as close to the surface as possible in order to eliminate any contamination on the surface.

An example of a processed AFM image of a silicon wafer, with a roughness S_a of 0.3 nm, is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 : Example of a flat surface (Silicon) measured by AFM ($2\ \mu\text{m} \times 2\ \mu\text{m}$, 1024 pixels x 1024 pixels). The surface roughness S_a is equal to 0.3 nm.

Roughness measurement using confocal microscopy

To perform roughness measurements using a 3D laser scanning confocal microscope (example here using a VK-9700, Keyence) it is recommended that the following instructions should be executed:

Optical tables or anti-vibration systems should be used to minimize the effect of natural vibrations on the alignment and measurement of the samples being examined.

- Place the sample on the sample stage.
- Adjust the microscope:
 - Select the objective with the desired magnification factor (recommended to start with the smallest factor and increase until the optimal magnification is achieved)
 - Adjust the position of the sample stage until the desired area is in position.
 - Adjust the focus, brightness of the laser induced image and if necessary the dynamic range. Areas on the sample may exhibit extremely different reflectance intensities and therefore the laser reflection intensity may be too strong or too weak. This can be adjusted using the dynamic range.
 - Set the z direction of the measuring range (vertical range: upper and lower position of the measuring range).
 - Step size, range and quality of the single measurement should be defined.
- Start the measurement.

To determine the surface roughness and its homogeneity, make a minimum of 3 measurements, changing the position between each measurement.

- To calculate the roughness S_a , it is necessary to use image processing software.

7. References

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